

Assessment of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of Polar and Non-Polar Extracts Against *Bacillus subtilis*

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ABSTRACT

The study looks at the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of several extracts against *Bacillus subtilis*, with a focus on the effectiveness of polar and non-polar solvents. Extracts were produced with methanol, ethanol, chloroform, and n-hexane to represent a variety of polarity. The antibacterial activity of each extract was assessed using a range of in vitro tests to obtain their MIC values. Polar solvents such as methanol and ethanol were expected to extract molecules with significant antibacterial action, whereas non-polar solvents like chloroform and n-hexane were expected to target other phytochemicals. The results showed significant diversity in inhibitory effectiveness, with methanol and ethanol extracts being the most potent against *B. subtilis*. This comparative investigation emphasises the importance of solvent selection in the extraction process and how it affects the antibacterial activity of plant-derived chemicals. The findings shed light on optimising extraction procedures for the development of effective antibacterial drugs.

KEYWORDS

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), *Bacillus subtilis*, Antimicrobial Activity, Polar Solvents, Non-Polar Solvents, Methanol Extracts, Ethanol Extracts, Chloroform Extracts, N-Hexane Extracts, Phytochemicals, Extraction Methods, Antibacterial Efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

The growing problem of antibiotic resistance needs ongoing research for new antimicrobial methods. *Bacillus subtilis*, a Gram-positive bacterium found in soil and the gastrointestinal tracts of mammals, is an important model organism for researching bacterial physiology and genetics. It also poses a significant concern as a pathogen capable of causing foodborne sickness and opportunistic infections in people. In response to this dilemma, researchers are increasingly looking to natural sources, particularly plant-derived chemicals, for their potential as antibacterial alternatives. Recent years have seen an increase in studies clarifying the antibacterial activities of plant extracts, opening up new pathways for drug discovery (Borges et al., 2020; Vouillamoz et al., 2021).

The efficacy of plant extracts in suppressing bacterial growth is closely tied to the solvents used during extraction. Solvents with differing polarity can preferentially extract distinct types of phytochemicals, each of which may contribute to the extract's overall antimicrobial effectiveness. Polar solvents such as methanol and ethanol are well-known for their capacity to extract a wide range of bioactive chemicals, including phenolics and flavonoids, which have been shown to have strong antibacterial properties against a variety of pathogens (Salehi et al., 2020). Non-polar solvents, such as chloroform and n-hexane, are better at extracting lipophilic chemicals like terpenes and alkaloids, which also have antibacterial characteristics (Shang et al., 2021).

This study seeks to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of plant extracts against *Bacillus subtilis*, with a particular emphasis on comparing the efficiency of polar and non-polar solvents. Using methanol, ethanol, chloroform, and n-hexane as extraction solvents, we hope to determine how solvent polarity effects the antibacterial potential of plant-derived chemicals. This study not only emphasises the importance of solvent selection in the extraction process, but also tries to discover the best extraction methods for producing powerful antimicrobial compounds from plants.

Understanding the complex relationship between solvent polarity and antimicrobial activity is critical for improving extraction techniques and furthering the development of new antimicrobial medicines. The findings of this study have important implications for addressing the urgent worldwide dilemma of antibiotic resistance and improving public health outcomes (Forni et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023).

Material and Methods

1g of *Spirulina* algae dry powder was mixed with 10 mL of distilled water. This extract was used to further determine the MIC value.

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration and Minimum antimicrobial activity

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest amount of a substance, medication, or natural plant extract that inhibits the development of bacteria, viruses, and fungi (Kin et al., 2022). The MIC against *Spirulina* algae dry powder was calculated by creating high-concentration solutions of medicines, natural compounds, or isolated bioactive compounds in vitro, incubating the solutions with various batches of cultured bacteria or fungi, and quantifying the findings using broth microdilution. While MIC is the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial agent used to suppress observable growth, it is also the lowest concentration of antimicrobial agents that kills bacteria and fungi (Tri et al., 2013). The most often used media are nutritional broth and Sabouraud's dextrose broth, which are known for their ability to sustain microbial growth and lack of inhibitors to popular antibiotics. The concentration of antimicrobial agents is adjusted to the correct level by combining stock antimicrobial agents with medium (Coc et al., 2015). To obtain a gradient, the adjusted antimicrobial agent is serially diluted in a 96-well plate.

Observation table and Results:

The minimum inhibitory activity of methanol extracts of Stage-1 LSC peel, Stage-2 MSC, Stage-3 HSC, Stage-4 VHSC, Stage-5 USC, and Stage-6 FC against *B. subtilis* (NCIM-2196) was determined using microtiter plates (well plate). *Spirulina* algae powder extract was employed at varying doses (50-200 µg/ml). Table 1 shows the negative control, *B. subtilis* culture, test sample, and positive control, gentamicin. The *Spirulina* algae powder extract was found to be the most effective concentration against *B. Subtilis*, with minimal activity against Stage-1 LSC (0.30 ± 0.10), 100µg/ml Stage-2 MSC (0.28 ± 0.16), 200µg/ml Stage-3 HSC (0.41 ± 0.01), 50µg/ml Stage-5 USC (0.27 ± 0.04), 200µg/ml Stage-4 VHSC (0.16 ± 0.04), and 150µg/ml Stage-6 FC (0.66 ± 0.03).

Table 1: Minimum inhibitory activity of methanol extract against *B. subtilis*

Methanol extract <i>B. Subtilis</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
Stage-1 LSC	0.54±0.03	0.47±0.03	0.33±0.09	0.30±0.10	0.0001	20.56
Stage-2 MSC	0.29±0.06	0.28±0.16	0.47±0.02	0.52±0.01	0.0002	16.01
Stage-3 HSC	0.48±0.12	0.61±0.18	0.59±0.08	0.41±0.01	0.0004	37.14
Stage-4 VHSC	0.50±0.17	0.21±0.02	0.58±0.15	0.16±0.04	0.0002	15.93
Stage-5 USC	0.27±0.04	0.43±0.02	0.55±0.03	0.43±0.17	0.0006	12.75
Stage-6 FC	0.67±0.02	0.72±0.08	0.66±0.03	0.43±0.16	0.0088	6.228
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>B. subtilis</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.77±0.06					

Figure 1: Minimum inhibitory activity of methanol extract against *B.subtilis*

The minimum inhibitory concentration of ethanol extracts of Stage-1 LSC, Stage-2 MSC, Stage-3 HSCs, Stage-4 VHSC, Stage-5 USC, and Stage-6 FC against *B. subtilis* (NCIM-2196) was determined using microtiter plates (well plates). Spirulina algae powder concentrations range from 50-200µg/ml.

Table 2 shows a negative control of *B. subtilis* culture, a test sample, and a positive control of gentamicin antibiotics. The extract of Spirulina algae powder was the most effective concentration of 200µg/ml ethanol extract of Stage-1 LSC (0.39±0.04), 100µg/ml Stage-2 MSC (0.31±0.16), 50µg/ml Stage-3 HSC (0.37±0.01), 100µg/ml & 150µg/ml Stage-5 USC (0.36±0.13), 200µg/ml Stage-4 VHSC (0.13±0.02), and 150µg/ml Stage-6 FC (0.36±0.02).

Table 2: Minimum inhibitory activity of ethanol extract against *B. subtilis*

Ethanol extract <i>B. Subtilis</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
Stage-1 LSC	0.82±0.14	0.51±0.07	0.41±0.09	0.39±0.04	0.0003	14.76
Stage-2 MSC	0.39±0.11	0.31±0.11	0.54±0.03	0.60±0.04	0.0003	15.80
Stage-3 HSC	0.37±0.01	0.59±0.05	0.56±0.07	0.61±0.21	0.0046	7.520
Stage-4 VHSC	0.35±0.08	0.56±0.03	0.24±0.07	0.13±0.02	0.0001	47.51
Stage-5 USC	0.30±0.03	0.36±0.03	0.36±0.13	0.37±0.06	0.0001	18.83
Stage-6 FC	0.36±0.02	0.41±0.04	0.57±0.07	0.52±0.10	0.0002	16.23
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.1					
Negative Control (<i>B. subtilis</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.77±0.06					

Figure 2: Minimum inhibitory activity of ethanol extract against *B. subtilis*

The lowest inhibitory concentration of chloroform extract of Stage-1 LSC, Stage-2 MSC, Stage-3 HSC, Stage-4 VHSC, Stage-5 USC, and Stage-6 FC against *B. subtilis* (NCIM-2196) was determined using microtiter plates (well plate). The harvested *Spirulina* algae powder was utilised at concentrations ranging from 50 to 200µg/mL. Table 3 shows *Subtilis* culture as a negative control, test sample, and gentamicin antibiotic as a positive control. The *Spirulina* algae powder chloroform extract was found to be the most effective concentration against *B. Subtilis*. The 50µg/ml chloroform extract of Stage-1 LSC (0.23±0.09), 50µg/ml Stage-2 MSC (0.32±0.07), 50µg/ml Stage-3 HSC (0.32±0.18), 50µg/ml Stage-5 USC (0.31±0.09), 200µg/ml Stage-4 VHSC (0.27±0.04), and 50µg/ml Stage-6 FC (0.37±0.05) showed minimal activity against *B. Subtilis*.

Table 3: Minimum inhibitory activity of chloroform extract against *B. subtilis*

Chloroform extract <i>B. Subtilis</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
Stage-1 LSC peel	0.23±0.09	0.59±0.33	0.56±0.08	0.49±0.09	0.0456	3.602
Stage-2 MSC peel	0.32±0.07	0.63±0.11	0.50±0.05	0.65±0.18	0.0046	7.504
Stage-3 HSC	0.54±0.21	0.61±0.06	0.51±0.02	0.32±0.18	0.0265	4.378
Stage-4 VHSC peel	0.33±0.02	0.64±0.19	0.57±0.14	0.27±0.04	0.0013	10.52
Stage-5 USC	0.31±0.09	0.61±0.07	0.64±0.05	0.65±0.02	0.0001	19.29
Stage-6 FC	0.37±0.05	0.57±0.15	0.62±0.10	0.59±0.12	0.0140	5.407
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>B. subtilis</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.77±0.06					

Figure 3: Minimum inhibitory activity of chloroform extract against *B. subtilis*

The minimum inhibitory activity of n-hexane extracts of Stage-1 LSC, Stage-2 MSC, Stage-3 HSC, Stage-4 VHSC, Stage-5 USC, and Stage-6 FC against *B. subtilis* (NCIM-2196) was determined using microtiter plates (well plate). The *Spirulina* algae powder extract was employed at various concentrations (50-200µg/ml). *B. subtilis* culture as a negative control and gentamicin as a positive control. The *Spirulina* algae powder extract was found to be the most effective concentration against *B. subtilis*. Other concentrations, including 200µg/ml n-hexane extract of Stage-1 LSC (0.40±0.10), 200µg/ml Stage-2 MSC (0.40±0.07), 50µg/ml Stage-3 HSC (0.35±0.03), 50µg/ml Stage-5 USC (0.26±0.00), 200µg/ml Stage-4 VHSC (0.31±0.00), and 50µg/ml Stage-6 FC (0.37±0.05) showed minimal activity against *B. subtilis*.

Table 4: Minimum inhibitory activity of hexane extract against *B. subtilis*

n-Hexane extract <i>B. Subtilis</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
Stage-1 LSC	0.62±0.12	0.49±0.16	0.45±0.02	0.40±0.10	0.0120	5.662
Stage-2 MSC	0.40±0.07	0.45±0.09	0.44±0.02	0.40±0.05	0.0001	17.90
Stage-3 HSC	0.35±0.03	0.61±0.08	0.58±0.02	0.57±0.01	0.0001	23.15
Stage-4 VHSC	0.71±0.07	0.65±0.02	0.36±0.15	0.31±0.00	0.0005	13.21
Stage-5 USC	0.26±0.00	0.51±0.11	0.55±0.02	0.36±0.16	0.0006	13.04
Stage-6 FC	0.43±0.09	0.84±0.03	0.62±0.11	0.40±0.14	0.0009	11.66
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>B. subtilis</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.77±0.06					

Figure 4: Minimum inhibitory activity of hexane extract against *B. subtilis*

Discussion:

The observed differences in inhibitory activity across the extracts highlight the importance of solvent selection in the extraction process. Methanol and ethanol extracts were the most potent against *Bacillus subtilis*, as expected given their capacity to extract a wide range of polar molecules with recognised antibacterial characteristics. In contrast, chloroform and n-hexane extracts, which represent non-polar solvents, showed significantly decreased inhibitory activity, implying that the extracted phytochemicals may have distinct mechanisms of action or lesser efficacy against *B. subtilis*. These findings highlight the significance of solvent polarity for developing extraction methods for antibacterial chemical identification. Optimising extraction methods to target certain classes of bioactive chemicals could speed up the discovery of potent antimicrobial medicines derived from plants, helping to battle antibiotic resistance and improve public health outcomes.

Conclusion

The current study looked at the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of methanol, ethanol, chloroform, and n-hexane extracts of *Spirulina* algae powder against *Bacillus subtilis* (NCIM-2196). Microtiter plate assays were used to evaluate inhibitory actions at extract concentrations ranging from 50 to 200 µg/ml.

The results show that *Spirulina* extracts have varied degrees of antibacterial activity depending on the solvent employed for extraction and the concentration of the extract. The methanol extract of Stage-1 LSC at 200 µg/ml showed considerable inhibition (0.30 ± 0.10), indicating its strong antibacterial activities. The ethanol extract of Stage-4 VHSC at 200 µg/ml (0.13 ± 0.02) shown significant inhibitory efficacy against *B. subtilis* growth.

Chloroform extracts had significant antibacterial action, with Stage-1 LSC at 50 µg/ml (0.23 ± 0.09) being especially effective. The n-hexane extracts inhibited Stage-1 LSC at 200 µg/ml (0.40 ± 0.10) and Stage-5 USC at 50 µg/ml (0.26 ± 0.00), indicating the potential of non-polar solvents in extracting bioactive chemicals from *Spirulina*.

The results show that *Spirulina* algae powder has promising antibacterial effects, especially at certain phases and extraction procedures. The extracts' potency changes with concentration and solvent, providing information for optimising extraction processes for maximum antibacterial efficacy. These findings lend support to additional research into *Spirulina*-derived chemicals as possible natural antibacterial agents, providing a more sustainable alternative to conventional antibiotics. Future study should focus on identifying and characterising the active ingredients responsible for the reported inhibitory effects, as well as assessing their modes of action against a wider range of microbial pathogens.

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